

FUNCTIONAL STYLISTIC FEATURES OF DOWNLOADS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK AND TRANSLATION ISSUES

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ANNOTATION

This article explores shifts in meaning of terms, which take place in a translation process. The analysis of shifts was made on the basis of various newspaper texts and their translations. In the first part of the article we take a close look at some scientific conceptions and approaches to the problem of translation quality assessment of both Russian and foreign scientists.

Keywords: *translation shifts, translation quality assessment, terms, minor errors, major errors*

Introduction

This article is devoted to the analysis of the texts of newspaper articles in which the terms occur, and their translations into Russian with the determination of the degree of discrepancy in the meaning of the word during translation. The analysis is based on newspaper texts various British and American editions and their translations. Since the birth of the science of translation, researchers have been concerned about the question assessment of the quality of translation, since in the process of translation inevitably there are losses in meaning or appear as a result of the use of translation transformations additional meanings that are not present in the original text. By misusing a particular word or using the wrong synonym in a translation, the translator runs the risk of changing the meaning of the text and its impact on the reader.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS.

Particle in modern German, English, Russian, Turkish, Uzbek some studies on presuppositions mutual analogy in their meaning, are created. On the topic of particle in Uzbek language M. Askarova O.Bazarov R.Rasulav U.E.Rahimov Z.Isakov A.B.Pardaev. Their comparative with the English and German language particle there are also partially studied works. But the features of particle events in the lexical-grammatical system have not yet been specially studied in our linguistics of conjugation. Therefore, based on the existing theoretical descriptions of this particle, studying the features of their expression in English and Uzbek, their methods of translation in comparative aspect and one of the necessary issues.

According to the appearance of the particle in the Uzbek language will have to learn in two these are:

1. Word particle: ахир, ҳатто (ки), наҳот (ки), ҳам, ғирт, фақат, атиги, нақ, худди, қоқ, ҳеч, сира, на...

2. Added particle: -ми, -чи, -а, -я, -у, -ю, - ку, -да, -оқ, -ёқ, -е, -гина, -кина, -қина, -ки, - дир....

In this place, it should be said that the English particle, in principle, is in the form of a word. In the Uzbek language, on the contrary, the particle in the form of an addition occupies a large place. Partikl words, similar to prepositions in terms of form, perform the function particle within the framework of three constructions in English. In particular, words that express a grammatic connection with other words, but do not have a clear lexical meaning – phraseology, quasy – modal verbs

and participle in the context of English-defining phrases perform the grammatic function of particle.

RESULT

Although all functional styles are in a unique way, various features are interrelated as a system, despite the fact that language is the main feature of a group of communication tools, it will not be enough to determine the requested functional style. Each functional style depends on a stable system at the stage of development of the

literary language, but it sometimes changes frequently as it passes from one period to the next. Therefore, the functional styles of the language are considered a historical series (category). Examples are enough to prove this concept. Consequently, the poetry (artistic) style of the functional style began to function as an independent style in the second half of the 16th century; newspaper style is separated from journalistic style; Like other functional styles, the style of speaking has undergone significant changes. The development of each style is predetermined by changes in the norms of the standard English and Uzbek languages. Changes in social conditions, scientific progress, and the development of cultural life have a great impact on this. The traditionally distinguished functional styles — scientific (popular science), formal, journalistic (popular), colloquial, artistic — are language subsystems, each of which is unique at five main levels: phonetic, morphological, lexical. , has syntactic and text structure features. Functional styles are distinguished by the possibility or not of the use of certain elements and structures, as well as their communication systems. For example, phonetic tools are important for the style of speaking: compliance with pronunciation standards, wide use of intonation; for the scientific method - syntactic: clear syntactic structure, direct order of words, wide use of words, wide use of various specific and specific systems, at the text level : logical, clear presentation structure (newspaper or magazine article). The text of the official style is characterized by the presence of special terms (commercial, legal, etc.), stamps, specialized foreign expressions, abbreviations, mixed words, absence of figurative means at the lexical level; at the syntactic level - complex structures are formed by the wide use of sentences in the passive tense of the verb.

CONCLUSION

Functional styles are found in written and spoken form. The speech style is characterized by the presence of short sentences, two-syllable words, phonetic and syntactic abbreviations. Artistic style combines three sub-styles: poetic style of language, emotional (artistic) prose style and dramatic style. There are common characteristics for each of these sub-styles and for individual sub-styles as well. Artistic

texts also have a number of difficulties, because they combine logical-intellectual information with figurative-emotional information. Reading popular style texts can be difficult. It should be noted that the peculiarity of this style is that some of the texts are scientific, and some are close to texts of other styles. Texts on journalism are distinguished by their coverage of political vocabulary, phraseological units, abbreviations, realisms, newspaper articles, expressions and various topics. Newspaper and magazine publications have a variety of headlines, including advertising and emotionally appealing ones. Two types of popular style are found in oral speech: speech style and the text of radio and television programs, as well as newspaper style in written speech. The written forms of the popular style are essays (philosophical, literary, moral) and journalistic articles (political, social, economic, etc.). The general purpose of the journalistic style is to influence public opinion, to convince the reader or listener that the opinion given by the author is the only true one, and to encourage him to accept the expressed opinion.

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